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PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF METFORMIN MICROSPHERES BY USING PENETRATION ENHANCER 0.5% EDTA

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ABSTRACT

The aim of project to prepare and evaluate the metformin microspheres with and without bio enhancer EDTA by using mucoadhesive polymers such as sodium alginate and hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose and to study release rate of metformin. The microsphere of metformin was prepared by sodium alginate and hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water with 0.5 % penetration enhancer in this solution 100 mg of metformin was added. Then this solution was added by drop by drop to 4 % calcium chloride solution with the help of 10 μ size syringe which produces spherical microspheres which was collected by filtering through whatman filter paper. The evaluation parameters for developed microspheres were angle of repose, particle size, bulk density, swelling index respectively. The release rate was studied for 5 hrs. By using UV visible double beam spectrophotometer at wavelength 232 nm represent that drug was released by controlled release mechanism. From this experimental study it was concluded that developed microspheres for metformin represent 24 μ size spherical shape with significant evaluation parameter and microsphere study of metformin microsphere with 0.5 % EDTA represent slight increase in release profile of metformin from developed metformin microsphere. It is clear that there is great deal of potential for the use of microsphere drug delivery formulations to treat diabetes, only few of these formulations have progressed enough in human studies to have proven their worth both in enhancing the efficacy of the drugs being delivered and minimizing the undesirable side effects.

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INTRODUCTION

Tremendous opportunities exist for utilizing advanced drug delivery systems for cancer treatment. One such formulation type that has already begun to fulfill its promise is injectable microencapsulated delivery systems. The terminology used to describe micro particulate formulations can sometimes be inconsistent and confusing to readers unfamiliar with the field. Essentially the term “microparticle” refers to a particle with a diameter of 1-1000 μm , within broad category of microparticles “microspheres” specifically refers to spherical microparticles and the subcategory of microcapsules applies to microparticles which have a core surrounded by a material which is distinctly different from that of core. The core may be solid, liquid or even gas despite the specific and logical subcategories. It is usually assumed that a formulation described as a microparticle is comprised of a fairly homogenous mixture of polymer and active agent.

There are numerable methods for use in application as diverse as carbonless paper to ion exchange resins to cosmetics to drug delivery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Metformin were supplied as gift sample from Indoco Remedies Mumbai, sodium alginate, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose and EDTA also supplied

Equipment used in the formulation of ocular gel for endophthalmitis Digital balance Japan (Model: AU220), UV-Spectrophotometer Shimadzu, FT-IR Spectrophotometer Shimadzu Japan (Model FTIR-8400S), DSC Mettler Toledo (Star system) , USP Dissolution Apparatus Eletrolab Mumbai (Model TDT-06P), Franz diffusion cell Electrolab Mumbai (Model TDT-08L)

Prior to development of dosage form, it is essential that certain fundamental physical and chemical properties of the drug molecules and other derived properties of drug determined. This information dictates many of the subsequent event approaches in formulation development. This first learning phase is known as preformulation.

Identification of metformin for its standard

Solubility test for metformin as per I.P

- 1) With water- freely soluble
- 2) With 95 % ethanol-slightly soluble
- 3) With ether- insoluble
- 4) With acetone-insoluble
- 5) With chloroform-insoluble
- 6) With dichloromethane-insoluble

Melting point of metformin is 240^oC

It complies with I.P standard hence it selected for future research work

Preparation of calibration curve of metformin

Accurate 0.1gm of metformin hydrochloride weighed and shaken with 70 ml of water for 15 min diluted to 100 ml with water and filter. Diluted 10 ml of filtrate to 100 ml with water and measure the absorbance of the resulting solution at the maximum at about 232 nm. The given sample of metformin powder contains 98.74% of metformin hydrochloride as per I.P standard

Preparation of mucoadhesive metformin microspheres

Ionic gelation technique

Microspheres containing metformin with and without bioenhancer EDTA were prepared by ionic gelation technique which involves reaction between sodium alginate and polycationic like calcium to produce hydrogel network of calcium alginate. Sodium alginate (1.5gm) and mucoadhesive hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose (0.5gm) were dissolved in distilled water (100ml) to form homogenous polymer solution and placed for 24-48 hr, complete swelling occurred. Then 0.1 gm of metformin and bioenhancer EDTA (0.5gm) added and mixed with magnetic stirrer to form viscous dispersion. Then prepared 4% of calcium chloride solution and 0.5 % v/v surfactant tween 80 added and mixed well. Then optimized concentration of calcium chloride solution is prepared and drop by drop addition was done with the help of 10 μ size syringe. The addition of droplet were retained in calcium chloride solution to complete the reaction and to produce spherical microsphere were collected by filtering on whatman filter paper and product which was separated washed rapidly with water to remove excess of calcium impurity and air dried.

Preparation of phosphate buffer solution having pH 6.8

Weigh accurately 28.80 gm. of disodium hydrogen phosphate and 11.45gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in sufficient water to produce 1000 ml

Evaluation of metformin microspheres

Angle of repose:

Angle of repose of metformin microspheres was obtained by the microspheres were passed through the funnel and collected on the paper then diameter and height of the pile of microspheres was measured

Bulk density:

Bulk density of metformin microspheres was obtained by the microspheres was placed in the measuring cylinder of the bulk density apparatus

Particle size:

Particle size of microspheres was obtained by using microscope. Firstly the least count of scale is obtained then particles are measured on 45x objective of microscope

Swelling index:

Swelling index of prepared metformin microspheres was measured by 0.5gm metformin microspheres with and without bio enhancer EDTA were added in 2ml of distilled water separately to the small measuring cylinder and this was kept for 24 hrs. From the displacement of water in the measuring cylinder the swelling index is calculated.

Study of release rate of metformin microspheres

Diffusion medium- the diffusion medium used was phosphate buffer pH 6.8 prepared in lab itself

Assembly of diffusion cell-

For in vitro diffusion studies the intestinal diffusion cell was designed as per the dimension. The diffusion cells were placed on the magnetic stirrers. The outlet of reservoir maintained at 37°C and was connected to water jacket of diffusion cell using rubber latex tubes. The receptor compartment was filled with fluid. Then the prepared intestinal

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of metformin microspheres with and without bioenhancer EDTA.

Sr.No	Evaluation parameter	Observation	
		A	B
1	Angle of Repose	22.30	23.02
2	Particle size	52.48μ	53.39μ
3	Swelling index	5%	10%
4	Bulk density		
	After 3 tap	0.42gm/ml	0.582gm/ml
	After 5 tap	0.47gm/ml	0.582gm/ml
	After 50 tap	0.675gm/ml	0.727gm/ml

A= Metformin microspheres with bioenhancer ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid

B= Metformin microspheres with bioenhancer ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid

Absorbance at wavelength 232 nm.

Sr.No	Time (min)	Absorbance	
		A	B
1	30	0.250	0.296
2	60	0.298	0.298
3	90	0.382	0.391
4	120	0.384	0.408
5	150	0.404	0.412
6	180	0.415	0.431

Cumulative % Drug Release.

Sr.No	Time (min)	Drug Release (%)	
		A	B
1	30	68.15	50.71
2	60	80.73	60.44
3	90	93.51	77.48
4	120	99.8	81.95
5	150	112.58	84.18
6	180	111.56	84.79

CONCLUSION

Thus the result shows that maximum drug release rate increases with increasing time. Mechanisms of metformin with and without penetration enhancer known by in vitro release pattern of drug. It can be concluded that mucoadhesive microspheres containing metformin with bioenhancer ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid shows good release profile as compared to microspheres containing metformin without bioenhancer ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid with significant evaluation parameter such as angle of repose, particle size, swelling index, bulk density etc.

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